

MONITOR STRATEGIC

REVISTĂ DE STUDII DE SECURITATE ȘI APĂRARE

ANUL XXVI • Nr. 3-4/2025

- ◆ Expert Views on Strategic Culture in Europe: Findings from a Survey across the Network of European Strategic Studies Institutions (NESSI)
- ◆ Strategic Perspectives of the European Defence Industry – Lessons from Modern Ground Combat System (MGCS) and the Future Combat Air System (FCAS)
- ◆ Strengthening the Legal Interoperability of NATO, the EU and Member States to Enhance the Legal Resilience of Their Collective Security Arrangements
- ◆ American Doctrines and Strategies in the Mediterranean Region

INSTITUTUL PENTRU STUDII POLITICE DE APĂRARE ȘI ISTORIE MILITARĂ

SUMMARY

NATO AND THE EU: DEVELOPMENTS IN A CHANGING INTERNATIONAL SYSTEM

DEVELOPMENTS WITHIN THE EU AND NATO / 5

Alexandru Lucinescu – Expert Views on Strategic Culture in Europe: Findings from a Survey across the Network of European Strategic Studies Institutions (NESSI) / 7

Radu Carp – *Readiness 2030* – A New Challenge for the Concept of European Defence / 22

Kamil Nečas, Vojtěch Müllner – From Wales to The Hague: The Evolution of NATO Commitments / 28

Darko Gjorgjioski – Strategic Perspectives of the European Defence Industry – Lessons from Modern Ground Combat System (MGCS) and the Future Combat Air System (FCAS) / 40

Andreea Tudor – Strengthening the Legal Interoperability of NATO, the EU and Member States to Enhance the Legal Resilience of Their Collective Security Arrangements / 50

Teodora Crina Popescu – Transitioning from a Security Consumer to a Security Provider? Kosovo's Quest for NATO Membership / 60

GLOBAL SECURITY / 65

Liana-Andreea Negoită – American Doctrines and Strategies in the Mediterranean Region / 67

Robert-Ionuț Stanciu – From Global Multipolarity to Regional Unipolarity: Theoretical Aspects of a New Approach to Security? / 76

Șerban-Filip Cioculescu – In Search of the “Necessary Enemy”: An Analysis of the Political-Military Conflict Between Israel and Iran Through the Lens of Ontological Security Theory and the Failure of Mutual Deterrence / 83

Liana-Andreea Negoită, Anca Theodora Popescu – From Convention to Contestation: The Evolving Concept of Prisoner of War in the Aftermath of the 2022 Russian Invasion of Ukraine / 102

ROMANIA'S SECURITY POLICY / 111

George-Alin Oprea – Romania and the Motivations Behind the Non-Recognition of Kosovo / 113

BOOK REVIEWS / 121

Andrei-Cristian Flore – *Battleground – Ten Conflicts that Explain the New Middle East*, Yale University Press, 2024, by Christopher Phillips / 123

Expert Views on Strategic Culture in Europe: Findings from a Survey across the Network of European Strategic Studies Institutions (NESSI)

Alexandru LUCINESCU, PhD

ABSTRACT

The Network of European Strategic Studies Institutions (NESSI) took shape in 2021 at the initiative of the Institut de Recherche Stratégique de l'École Militaire (IRSEM), the strategic research institute of the French Ministry of Armed Forces, and currently brings together 20 research institutes affiliated with national defence establishments from 19 European countries (Austria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom). NESSI is designed to operate as a platform for expertise on strategic issues and facilitates, among its members, both the exchange of knowledge and the sharing of perspectives on a regular basis. The presidency of NESSI is annually assumed by one of its members on a rotating basis, and in 2025 this position was held by the Institute for Political Studies of Defence and Military History (IPSDMH) within the Romanian Ministry of National Defence. As an original contribution to the attainment of one key objective pursued by NESSI, the development of a common strategic culture, IPSDMH conducted a network-wide survey, the findings of which were presented on the sidelines of the annual conference "Preparing for Turbulent Times – Reshaping Europe's Defence: Challenges, Lessons Learned and Possible Scenarios," held in Bucharest from 16 to 19 September 2025. IPSDMH's research staff contributed as follows: Dr Daniela Şişcanu and Dr Şerban-Filip Cioculescu drafted and circulated the survey, and Dr Alexandru Lucinescu analysed the results.

Keywords: NESSI, European strategic culture, European defence, threat perception, NATO, European Union, United States of America

Alexandru Lucinescu (PhD in Intelligence and National Security) is a senior researcher at the Institute for Political Studies of Defence and Military History.

A. Methodological approach

The survey was launched in April 2025 and circulated for five months among experts from NESSI and resulted in 13 responses. The questionnaire was distributed and the responses collected electronically (by email), with all responses subsequently anonymised before being processed and analysed, in order to encourage more forthcoming answers. The survey comprised 15 items pertaining to current

and relevant issues of European defence, in terms of threats and possible ways of addressing them through NATO and EU, as well as by individual European states. Each item was formulated as a declarative statement, and respondents were invited to express their views using a five-point Likert scale: strongly agree, somewhat agree, not sure, somewhat disagree, strongly disagree. In addition, several items allowed respondents to provide open-ended comments, thereby complementing the

closed-ended responses obtained through the Likert scale. All items were subjected to quantitative analysis, with the number of respondents and the corresponding percentage reported for each of the five Likert-scale response options. In addition, for the items that included open-ended responses, a qualitative content analysis was carried out, whereby comments were systematically grouped into categories corresponding to the main issues identified. Furthermore, a comparative analysis was undertaken for selected items, encompassing both the distributions across the Likert-scale answer choices and the open-ended comments. Beyond the numerical and categorical comparison, the results were also interpreted, with attention to the substantive insights that emerged from the observed differences and similarities. For the purpose of the analysis, the survey items were grouped into two main categories. The first category addressed respondents' perceptions of threats to European security (Q2, Q12), while the second focused on the approaches to addressing security threats, whether by Eu-

ropean states (Q1, Q3, Q4, Q5, Q6, Q7, Q11) or through the European Union and NATO (Q8, Q9, Q10, Q13, Q14, Q15).

Despite the relatively small number of participants, the validity of the survey results for grasping the contours of strategic culture among NESSI members retains its significance, as the expertise of the contributors lends considerable weight to the data, thereby compensating, to a relevant extent, for the limited size of the sample. The survey reflected the security situation at the time of its drafting, and even though events have since evolved, its items may still be considered to have preserved their relevance.

B. Examination of the findings

1. Perceptions of security threats to Europe

A broad majority endorsed this assessment (76.9%), and the strength of this prevailing positive orientation is underscored by the clear majority of respondents (61.5%) who

Q2. *The military threats from the Russian Federation represent the most significant security threat to my country in the current geopolitical climate.*

offered unqualified agreement, a share representing nearly 80% of those in agreement. Yet the presence of a sizeable minority, comprising nearly one quarter of the respondents (23.1%), who expressed partial disagreement

introduces a level of reservation that qualifies the predominant opinion. At the same time, the absence of any strong disagreement indicates that such reservations fall short of constituting a fundamental challenge to the

assessment. Finally, the lack of undecided responses suggests that the issue prompted all respondents to adopt a position, even if in some cases that position was articulated only in qualified terms. The sizeable gap between those who agree and those who disagree indicates an absence of polarisation and a broad tilt toward agreement.

The principal argument for viewing the Russian Federation as the foremost security threat was that it constitutes the only direct, existential threat to Europe. By contrast, responses expressing reservations argued that the Russian Federation was either comparable in importance to other threats – namely,

a potential invasion of Taiwan by China and the combined effects of climate change and instability arising from volatile regions of the world – or of lesser relevance when compared to threats emanating from Europe’s southern neighbourhood (e.g., North Africa, the Sahel, the Red Sea). The responses highlighted variations in how threats are perceived, both in their geographical distribution – distinguishing between those emanating from NATO’s eastern flank, Europe’s southern neighbourhood, and the Indo-Pacific region – and in their nature, differentiating between military threats posed by Russia and China and non-military threats such as climate change.

Q12. *Cyber threats, terrorism, and hybrid warfare will become more frequent in the EU space in the near future.*

A large majority, amounting to 84.6%, endorses this assessment, and the strength of this broad consensus is underscored by the marked predominance of unqualified agreement, which represents a clear majority both among all respondents (69.2%) and, even more strongly, among those expressing agreement (81.8%). It is nonetheless noteworthy that partial agreement and indecision together account for over a quarter of the total respondents (30.8%), indicating that those without full certainty regarding the precise short-term

evolution of these threats represent a non-negligible share. Importantly, no respondent expressed disagreement, and as a result the opinions are non-polarised, clearly indicating that the discussion concerns primarily the extent to which these threats are expected to increase in the near term.

Responses to Q2 and Q12, considered together, point to Europe facing a high level of security threats, consisting of a mixture of conventional and unconventional threats that are generated by both state and non-state actors.

2. Approaches to addressing security threats affecting Europe

2.1. At the level of European states

The 100% agreement stands out and indicates that achieving European defence autonomy is unanimously regarded as the overarch-

ing goal to which all available resources should be committed. The breadth of this consensus is well grounded in a consistent majority (76.9%) expressing unqualified agreement. Nevertheless, the fact that nearly a quarter of respondents express certain reservations suggests that, despite the unanimity on the principle, the issue of costs remains a matter of concern.

Q1. *We need a greater defence autonomy in Europe despite the significant financial and other related costs.*

These opinions convey both a sense of urgency in reaching this objective and the perception that defence autonomy constitutes an appropriate response to military and non-military threats, regardless of their geographic origin or the type of international actors behind them. The importance attributed to strategic autonomy rests on two main arguments: the belligerent policy of the Russian Federation and the uncertainty surrounding the US commitment to Europe's conventional and nuclear defence. With regard to the latter, it has been suggested that the prospect of US disengagement from Europe may, in fact, constitute a form of strategic ambiguity deliberately cultivated by the Trump Administration towards NATO's European members as a means of exerting leverage to increase their defence expenditures. It was noted that European defence autonomy could be pursued independently by the EU, by NATO through its European

Pillar, or jointly by the two organisations, in which case greater reliance should be placed on the Berlin Plus arrangements. Regarding the financial burden of building defence autonomy, it was emphasised that the wealthier European states are expected to shoulder a larger share. As for the feasibility of increasing defence autonomy, it was indicated that it is unlikely for it to be achieved in the short to medium term, because it largely depends on the prevailing strategic culture among European states which is currently unsupportive of it and whose change requires a long-term process. As for the feasibility of increasing defence autonomy, it was noted that its achievement in the short to medium term is unlikely, as it largely depends on the currently prevailing strategic culture among European states – a culture which tends to be unsupportive of such an effort and whose transformation requires a long-term process. An important

conceptual distinction was drawn between strategic autonomy – understood as reduced reliance on the US – and the enhancement of military capabilities, with the latter rather than the former identified as the paramount goal for European states. From this perspective, sustaining US engagement in Europe and strengthening the military capabilities of Eu-

ropean states are mutually reinforcing rather than mutually exclusive; possessing both robust national military capabilities and a firm US presence in Europe would allow European states to achieve greater security. The process of advancing European defence autonomy thus emerges as practically challenging and conceptually open to discussion.

Q6. My country should play a more active role in strengthening European defence cooperation.

The data reveal a strong majority of 84.6% expressing agreement, within which 63.5% offered an unambiguous endorsement in the form of strong agreement. However, the strength of the broad consensus is tempered by the fact that only a narrow majority (53.8%) of the total respondents expressed unqualified agreement, while nearly half of them (46.2%) inclined towards a more qualified position on this issue, either by adopting partial agreement (30.8%) or by remaining undecided (15.4%). It is also relevant in this respect that, among respondents expressing agreement, more than a quarter (25.7%) offered only partial endorsement. The absence of disagreement shows that, despite these nuances, the overall orientation remains firmly positive, with the opinion displaying a non-polarised character.

The main conditions for enhancing involvement in European defence cooperation are considered to be broad political and public

support for strengthening European autonomous defence as a means of reducing exclusive reliance on NATO, together with the availability of the necessary material and human resources. It is mentioned that an appropriate balance must be found between political commitment to defence cooperation and the development of adequate capabilities, with the latter taking precedence; the underlying rationale is that capability development provides the substance without which political dimension of defence cooperation would remain merely aspirational. Among the priority areas identified for defence cooperation are multinational research, collaborative capability development programmes, and the establishment of multinational military structures. A general conclusion that can be drawn is that a more visible national role in European defence cooperation rests on public and political endorsement, supported by adequate resources.

Q5. *The willingness of your country to join various European defence initiatives is more dependent on political will than resources.*

There is only a fragile majority built around agreement, with 53.9% of respondents endorsing this view. Yet the position of those offering unreserved support does not cross the threshold of a majority of respondents standing well below it at 30.8%. The fragility of this majority is further accentuated, on the one hand, by the fact that the share of partial supporters (23.1%) is relatively close to that of the unequivocal supporters, representing 42.8% of all those in agreement, and, on the other hand, by the existence of a group of undecided respondents whose proportion is identical to that of the strong supporters (30.8%). To this must be added the presence of a non-negligible segment expressing partial disagreement (15.4%). The absence of respondents expressing strong disagreement nonetheless provides an element of reinforcement for the prevailing position. The distribution does not reflect polarisation but rather a fragmented pattern of opinions, with a relative majority in agreement, a smaller share in disagreement, and a substantial proportion undecided.

In support of the claim that political will plays only a secondary role, it is argued that resources, particularly financial and logistical, are indispensable for translating political intentions into practice. At the same time, it

is noted that neither political will nor resources constitute the ultimate foundation for participation in European defence initiatives, as this role belongs to national strategic culture, which must be aligned with such an orientation in defence policy.

Taken in conjunction, the responses to Q1, Q6 and Q5 suggest that the enhancement of European defence autonomy rests primarily on greater engagement by European states which, in turn, presupposes the alignment of resources with political commitment, supported by a strategic culture consistent with this objective.

Disagreement with this assessment constitutes a broad majority amounting to 84.7%, within which the dominant view is partial disagreement, representing 61.8% of all those opposing the statement. This indicates that the prevailing disagreement is overall less categorical. The strength of the broad consensus against the assessment is further tempered by the presence of 15.4% of respondents who expressed only partial agreement with the assessment. Finally, the absence of undecided respondents demonstrates that their opinions on this issue are firmly crystallised. A further conclusion, grounded in the distribution of all responses, is that opinions are neither fragmented nor polarised, but instead reflect a clear and consistent orientation.

Q4. Strengthening national defence capabilities alone is sufficient to address current security challenges.

It is argued that strong national defence capabilities must be complemented by the consolidation of a European strategic culture, a robust willingness to defend the nation – particularly in relation to high-cost military capabilities – enhanced societal resilience and preparedness, effective mechanisms for countering disinformation, the establishment of an EU nuclear umbrella independent of the United States, a legal framework supportive of technological innovation, and command structures at EU level developed to a degree comparable to those of NATO. The reference to burden-sharing suggests that the issue should be considered not solely within the transatlantic framework of NATO, but equally within the dynamics of intra-European relations.

Q3. There is a strong will to fight in my country in the case of a Russian military aggression.

No majority position emerges on this issue, with disagreement at 38.5%, thus exceeding both agreement (30.8%) and indecision (30.8%), and giving relative preponderance to disagreement. Since 60% of those disagreeing fall into the category of partial disagreement, the prevailing form of disagreement is more qualified than categorical in nature. Among those expressing agreement, no dominant option is discernible, as both unconditional and partial agreement are equally represented (15.4% each). It is equally relevant that respondents in agreement and those undecided each account for the same share of the total, namely 30.8%. Overall, the results indicate that opinions are fragmented rather than polarised, with a relative leaning towards disagreement.

Effective means of strengthening the will to fight are identified as the incorporation of patriotic education into the formal curriculum

with support from the Ministry of Defence, the cultivation of patriotic values within the family, framing national defence as the protection of home, family, and lifestyle, reinforcing trust in state institutions, including the armed forces, articulating clearly the value of national sovereignty, fostering a sense of national unity, and, finally, broadening the scope of conscription. It is suggested that a conceptual distinction should be drawn between the *will to fight* and the broader *will to stand for one's country*, on the grounds that the former is only one component of the latter. The *will to fight* is understood as specific to wartime and to combatants, whereas *the will to stand for one's country* applies in both war and peace, engaging the entire population and the full range of activities essential to national survival; given its broader scope, the will to stand for one's country is regarded as deserving priority.

Q11. *A rapidly militarising Europe will better deter Russia from committing another aggression*

The level of agreement is very high (92.3%), and the strength of this broad consensus is reinforced by the fact that, among those supporting this position, 66.6% express unconditional endorsement, while only 33.3% offer qualified support. The low proportion of undecided respondents (7.7%) suggests that most participants have already formed firm opinions on

the issue, while the complete absence of disagreement indicates that the views expressed are non-polarised.

The predominant view, amounting to 61.5% of respondents, is built around disagreement with this assessment, and the strength of this prevailing orientation results from the fact that it consists exclusively of respondents

Q7. The rearming of Europe could contribute to escalating tensions and could ultimately precipitate a military conflict with Russia.

who strongly disagree. However, this position is moderated by almost a quarter of respondents (23.1%) remaining undecided and a smaller share (15.4%) expressing only partial agreement. The significant difference between agreement and disagreement, in favour of the latter, indicates that the predominant opinion is clearly negative, but not polarised. Moreover, the sizeable proportion of undecided respondents suggests that overall opinions are not yet fully crystallised. Overall, there is no fragmentation of opinions but rather a well-discernible disagreement.

The balancing of the defence build-up of European states with the avoidance of war with Russia is considered possible through effective strategic communication and diplomacy. Such measures could prevent a security dilemma by making clear to the Russian Federation that the driving factor behind these efforts is the pursuit of defence autonomy and not aggression against it. On the other hand, it is argued that the defence build-up is unlikely to trigger an armed conflict with the Russian Federation while it is still underway, since Russia is not currently in a position to wage war against EU and NATO states, and that once completed it will not have such an effect because it will

operate as a powerful deterrent against Russia. Unlike the arguments favouring a military build-up, it is also maintained that the most credible way of convincing the Russian Federation of the absence of aggressive intentions, and thus of eliminating any prospect of being drawn into a war with it, is for European states not to engage in a military build-up, since the absence of significant military capabilities simply renders any aggression against the Russian Federation unfeasible. Low European defence spending signals to Moscow the absence of aggressive intentions.

Reading Q11 and Q7 in conjunction, it could be maintained that confidence in the European military build-up as an effective deterrent against the Russian Federation is less robust than would appear from Q11 alone, since the responses to Q7 express concern that manifests either as uncertainty about the implications of such a build-up in relation to the Russian Federation or as partial conviction that its outcome could ultimately be a military confrontation with the Russian Federation. Consequently, these questions suggest that the military build-up should be pursued with great caution regarding its implications for the relationship with the Russian Federation.

Q8. *The EU member states need to develop a grand strategy to project and build a credible European defence posture.*

2.2. Within the frameworks of EU and NATO

For the second time, the 100% agreement threshold is reached, this time indicating that the adoption of a grand strategy at the level of EU is imperative. Within this total consensus, however, there is a consistent minority of 30.8% that expresses qualified agreement, to the effect that the need for such a strategy is not to be endorsed without further scrutiny.

Among the objectives identified for inclusion in an EU grand strategy are the development of a common threat and risk assessment, the financing of defence procurement from the EU general budget, joint military capability development, defence production and defence-related research and development, intelligence sharing, the harmonisation of defence-related national legal frameworks, the safeguarding of liberal democracy as the EU's defining way of life, greater European defence autonomy, fair burden-sharing, the regular issuance of EU strategic documents, and stronger EU–NATO cooperation. It is thus emphasised that an EU grand strategy should be grounded in a common security culture, should provide effective financial, scientific,

economic, and normative instruments, and should foster a well-balanced contribution among EU member states.

Linking Q8 to Q1, the other item that generated 100% agreement, it can be observed that the enhancement of defence autonomy in Europe and the development of an EU grand strategy emerge not only as absolute priorities but also as convergent objectives.

A large majority of respondents (77.0%) disagree with this assessment, but most of them – that is, 60% of all those in disagreement – express only partial disagreement. The strength of this disagreement is moderated, albeit only to a limited extent, by the 15.4% of respondents who expressed categorical agreement, while the difference between disagreement and agreement remains too large in favour of the former to produce a polarisation of opinion. The fact that the level of uncertainty is low (7.7%) indicates that opinions are, for the most part, well crystallised. In sum, disagreement is the predominant view, and the distribution of responses shows no fragmentation of opinions.

Arguments in support of abandoning the unanimous consent system include avoiding the paralysis of CSDP decisions due to single-state blockages, limiting external

Q9. *Preserving the current system of unanimous consent within the EU on defence issues is essential to reinforcing the stability and legitimacy of the EU's decisions and policies.*

interference in the EU defence decision-making process when third countries are in a position to exert significant influence on an EU member state, facilitating the formation of coalitions of the willing and unilateral initiatives among EU members, and enabling timely decision-making in crises. As a means of facilitating the abandonment of unanimity,

it has been proposed that qualified majority voting should require a supermajority threshold – set not merely above 50% but potentially as high as 90%. At the same time, a note of caution is expressed, emphasising that the principal risk of moving away from consensus lies in the possible fuelling of nationalism across the EU.

Q10. *Introducing the qualified majority voting system in respect to EU defence matters could affect the right to exert national sovereignty.*

A comfortable majority of 69.3% of respondents support this assessment. However, most within this category – 66.7% – express only partial support, which somewhat reduces the strength of the majority. An even stronger effect in this direction comes from the significant share of disagreement, amounting to 30.8%, that is, well above one quarter of the respondents; the implications are particularly important given that categorical disagreement accounts for 50% of all dissenting opinions. Consequently, agreement emerges as the predominant orientation, without reaching the level of consensus. The absence of uncertainty indicates that views on this matter are well crystallised, and the uneven distribution of responses precludes fragmentation.

Arguments in favour of adopting a qualified majority voting system emphasise that all

unions imply a certain degree of sovereignty loss, with the EU being no exception. From this perspective, the defence of national sovereignty cannot be used to justify blocking initiatives supported by a clear majority of EU members. In turn, those cautious about this voting system stress that it disproportionately affects smaller member states.

A joint consideration of Q9 and Q10 can be interpreted as indicating a high level of agreement that the stability and legitimacy of the EU's decisions within the CSDP are not undermined by the limits to sovereignty inherent in membership of an effectively functioning EU in the field of defence. It may further be observed that this understanding appears to resonate more strongly with large EU member states than with smaller ones.

Q14. *Defence cooperation between the European Union and NATO will remain a key factor for transatlantic security.*

A very consistent majority of 92.3% supports this assessment, with the consensus further strengthened by the fact that 74.9% of those in agreement express categorical support. The level of uncertainty is limited to only 7.7%, while no respondent expressed disagreement. Taken together, these results indicate that agreement takes the form of a broad consensus that is non-polarised, non-fragmented,

and marked by a high degree of crystallisation, owing to the predominance of categorical endorsement within the overall support.

No clear majority emerges with respect to this assessment, although agreement holds relative preponderance, approaching the threshold of a majority with 46.2% of respondents. It is noteworthy, however, that this agreement is not particularly strong, since only 16.7% of

Q15. *The USA will continue to keep its commitment to guaranteeing the security of Europe.*

those in agreement express a categorical position. The share of undecided respondents is significant, both in absolute terms (38.5%) and in relative terms, the latter being evident from the fact that it equals the proportion of respondents who express partial agreement (38.5%). The strength of agreement is further weakened by the presence of a non-negligible share of categorical disagreement (15.4%). Consequently, there is neither consensus nor even a predominant orientation, but rather a lack of crystallisation of views, with opinions

distributed mainly between partial agreement and indecision.

Confidence in the US commitment rests mainly on the assumption that the United States guarantees Europe’s security primarily in pursuit of its own interests, while caution is reflected in the view that, at best, the US will provide only nuclear deterrence, leaving conventional deterrence to Europeans, and, at worst, may withdraw nuclear deterrence altogether, thereby compelling Europeans to develop their own nuclear capabilities.

Q13. *The EU could effectively provide a common defence for Europe with less US involvement in NATO.*

This assessment does not obtain a majority, yet agreement is expressed by 46.2% of respondents, a proportion approaching that of a simple majority. However, within this relatively preponderant position, the strength of agreement is diluted by the fact that only 33.3% of those in agreement express a categorical view. At the opposite end, a significant share of respondents (30.8%) express disagreement, with the strength of this position reinforced by the fact that 75% of them adopt a categorical stance. Indecision also remains considerable, at 23.1%, indicating that views on this issue are insufficiently crystallised. Taken together, the configuration suggests that, despite the relative preponderance of agreement, its weight is undermined by both the high share of undecided respondents and the consistent strength of disagreement. Overall, no consensus or predominant orientation emerges, and the distribution of responses points rather to a lack of crystallisation

than to actual polarisation of opinions.

An aggregated reading of Q2, Q3, Q7, Q12, Q13, and Q15 indicates the difficult security situation currently faced by European states. They are confronted with a high level of both military and non-military threats that are highly likely to intensify, while the willingness

of their populations to fight for the defence of the homeland remains limited. At the same time, there is significant concern regarding the ability of the military build-up to deter Russian aggression, coupled with insufficient confidence both in the firmness of the US commitment to guarantee European security and in the capacity of EU member states to ensure their own defence in the context of a reduced US engagement within NATO.

3. Final considerations

An intuitive and easy-to-follow overview of the survey results can be provided on the basis of a set of criteria specifically developed for this purpose. Thus, the items are organised according to the presence or absence of a majority opinion. Items for which a majority was recorded are further subdivided according to whether the majority expressed agreement or disagreement. Items without a majority opinion are, in turn, classified according to the relative preponderance of agreement (strongly agree and somewhat agree) or disagreement (strongly disagree and somewhat disagree), given that no item showed indecision (“not sure”) as the relatively dominant position. Within each of these categories, items

SYNOPSIS

MAJORITY AGREEMENT

strongly agree + somewhat agree

- **100%** We need a greater defence autonomy in Europe despite the significant financial and other related costs
- **100%** The EU member states need to develop a grand strategy to project and build a credible European defence posture
- **92.3%** Defence cooperation between the European Union and NATO will remain a key factor for Transatlantic security
- **92.3%** A rapidly militarizing Europe will better deter Russia from committing another aggression
- **84.6%** Cyber threats, terrorism, and hybrid warfare will become more frequent in the EU space in the near future
- **84.6%** My country should play a more active role in strengthening European defence cooperation
- **76.9%** The military threats from the Russian Federation represent the most significant security threat to my country in the current geopolitical climate (**23.1% somewhat disagree**)
- **69.3%** Introducing the qualified majority voting system in respect to EU defence matters could affect the right to exert national sovereignty (**30.8% strongly disagree + somewhat disagree**)
- **53.9%** The willingness of your country to join various European defence initiatives is more dependent on political will than resources (**30.8% not sure; 15.4% somewhat disagree**)

MAJORITY DISAGREEMENT

strongly disagree + somewhat disagree

- **84.7%** Strengthening national defence capabilities alone is sufficient to address current security challenges
- **77%** Preserving the current system of unanimous consent within the EU on defence issues is essential to reinforcing the stability and legitimacy of the EU's decisions and policies (**15.4% strongly agree**)
- **61.5%** The rearming of Europe could contribute to escalating tensions and could ultimately precipitate a military conflict with Russia (**23.1% not sure; 15.4% somewhat agree**)

UNDECIDED

strongly agree + somewhat agree

- **46.2%** The EU could effectively provide a common defence for Europe with less US involvement in NATO (**23.1% not sure 30.8% strongly disagree + somewhat disagree**)
 - **46.2%** The USA will continue to keep its commitment to guaranteeing the security of Europe (**38.5% not sure; 15.4 strongly disagree**)
- strongly disagree + somewhat disagree
- **38.5%** There is a strong will to fight in my country in the case of a Russian military aggression (**30.8% strongly agree + somewhat agree; 30.8% not sure**)

are ranked in descending order according to the percentage corresponding to the specific response option that defines the respective category. All these aspects are reflected in the synopsis below.

This synopsis points to the existence of nine issues with respect to which either no majority opinion is present, or such an opinion does exist but is accompanied by a minority of agreement or disagreement – in the form of either strong or somewhat agreement/disagreement – that reaches at least 15%. The threshold for identifying such minority positions was set at a lower, yet still significant, level in order to capture a wide array of incongruence points. The hierarchy of the items identified reflects, in sequence, the absence of a majority opinion and the presence of such an opinion, in both cases ranking being carried out in ascending order of the percentage corresponding to the relatively predominant opinion or to the majority opinion, respectively. Listed in the order indicated above, the nine issues are as follows:

1. National will to fight in the event of a Russian military aggression
2. Effectiveness of defence provided within the EU framework under reduced US involvement in NATO

3. The credibility of US commitments to NATO's collective defence in Europe

4. The role of political will and resource availability in shaping national decisions to join European defence initiatives

5. The contribution of a rearmed Europe to escalating tensions with Russia and precipitating a military conflict with it

6. Implications of adopting qualified-majority voting in the EU's CSDP for national sovereignty of EU member states

7. The perceived level of threat posed by the Russian Federation

8. Implications of adopting qualified-majority voting in the EU's CSDP for the stability and legitimacy of the EU's decisions and policies

9. The extent to which enhanced national defence capabilities are sufficient to successfully cope with current security threats

Focusing discussion on these nine issues – which account for a significant 60% of the total number of survey items – could be said to contribute to the consolidation of a common strategic culture among NESSI members.